

Polarographic Behaviour of Benzyl Disulphide and *p*-Tolyl Disulphide in Aqueous *N,N'*-Dimethylsulphoxide Buffers

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Manuscript received 2 August 1992, revised 11 October 1993, accepted 16 November 1993

Polarographic reduction of benzyl disulphide shows two waves corresponding to the reduction of S-S and CH₂-SH bonds, while the reduction of *p*-tolyl disulphide occurs over one two-electron wave. Effect of pH, nature of waves and reduction mechanism have been discussed. In this connection kinetic studies for the decomposition of S-S bond in *p*-tolyl disulphide have been carried out at different pH values.

Disulphides are readily reducible at the dropping mercury electrode, and undergo two-electron reduction processes¹. Over the pH-range 2-9 one-electron or two-electron waves are obtained² depending on the catalytic effect of mercury. In the present paper the polarographic reduction of benzyl disulphide as an aliphatic disulphide and *p*-tolyl disulphide as an aromatic disulphide in 30% (v/v) dimethylsulphoxide-aqueous universal buffer³ solutions, has been carried out to elucidate the mechanism of their electrode processes using DC technique. In this connection kinetic studies of the decomposition of *p*-tolyl disulphide at different pHs were also carried out.

Results and Discussion

Figs. 1 and 2 represent the polarograms respectively of benzyl disulphide and *p*-tolyl disulphide. In absence of maximum suppressor, the polarograms of benzyl disulphide consist of one reduction waves in the pH range 3.76-4.56. On increasing the pH to 5.29, a second wave appears at more negative potentials accompanied by a maximum of the first kind (Fig. 1). At pHs > 8.18, the second wave completely disappears and the polarogram is characterised by a maximum instead of the second wave. The polarogram of *p*-tolyl disulphide consist of one reduction wave at all the pHs used. The limiting currents of all the

Fig. 1. Polarograms of 2.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ benzyl disulphide in universal buffer solution containing 30% DMSO at pH: (—) 3.76, (---) 4.56, (...) 5.29, (-·-) 7.87, (o) 8.18 (*), 9.07 and (x) 9.95.

waves gradually decrease and the half-wave potentials shift to more negative values with increasing pH of the media. The shift of the half-wave potential with increasing pH can be represented by the equations,

$$E_{1/2} = 0.07 - 0.07 \text{ pH} \quad \text{benzyl disulphide}$$

$$E_{1/2} = -0.13 - 0.05 \text{ pH} \quad \text{p-tolyl disulphide}$$

The diffusion-controlled nature of the waves at pHs 3.6 and 9.0 was examined by plotting

Fig. 2. Polarograms of 2.5×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} *p*-tolyl disulphide in universal buffer solution containing 30% DMSO at pH: (—) 3.62, (---) 4.48, (...) 5.33, (—•—) 8.07, (o) 9.98 and (•) 10.67.

i_d vs C (mM). Straight line passing through the origin within concentration range 0.0–0.4 mM were obtained.

The reversibility of the electrode process was investigated by logarithmic analysis of the shape of the wave using the following relation for the reversible reduction of a dimer⁴,

$$E = \text{constant} + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln(i_d - i)/i^2$$

The values of the slopes (Table 1) indicate two-electron transfer process at all pHs. For the second wave of benzyl disulphide, a four-electron

TABLE 1—VALUES OF SLOPE

Benzyl disulphide		<i>p</i> -tolyl disulphide	
pH	Slope	pH	Slope
3.76	0.031	3.21	0.032
5.29	0.043 (first wave)	8.07	0.035
9.95	0.026	9.95	0.026

process can be predicted. These results were further confirmed by plotting current-time curves (Fig. 3) during controlled potential electrolysis at pHs 3.6 and 6.0 for both the compounds and the number of electrons were calculated using Faraday's laws (Table 2).

Fig. 3. Current time curves for (I) benzyl disulphide at pH (—) 3.6 and (---) 6.0; (II) *p*-tolyl disulphide at pH (—•—) 3.6 and (—••—) 6.0.

TABLE 2—DATA OF CONTROLLED POTENTIAL COULOMETRY FOR DISULPHIDES

Compd.	pH	Wt of substance $\times 10^{-3}$	Mol wt.	$Q = \int_0^t i dt$	Number of electron
Benzyl disulphide	3.6	5.23	246.39	4.43	2.12; 2.20
	6.0	5.23	246.39	8.83	4.31; 4.0
<i>p</i> -Tolyl disulphide	3.6	5.23	246.39	5.0	2.44; 2.0
	6.0	2.51	246.39	1.63	1.66; 2.0

In aqueous organic solvent it was observed that the limiting current of *p*-tolyl disulphide wave gradually decreased with time. As expected, due to resonance between the lone-pair of electrons of sulphur and aromatic benzene ring the ArS-SAr bond fission occurred with the production of thiol group. On the other hand, S-S bond for benzyl disulphide is stabilised by the presence of aralkyl group. At appropriate time intervals, solutions of *p*-tolyl disulphide at various pHs were analysed polarographically by measuring the limiting currents of the polarograms at potentials corresponding to the plateau position of the waves. The rate constant obtained from the semilogarithmic plots are 0.011, 0.016 and $0.02 \pm 0.002 \text{ min}^{-1}$ at pHs 2.53, 8.18 and 9.95 respectively. These values indicate the increase of the rate of S-S bond fission with increasing pH of the medium due to the increase of stability of thiol anion formed.

Reduction mechanism : On the basis of the above results and by considering the mechanisms proposed by several authors for aliphatic and aromatic disulphides, it could be concluded that :
(a) Reduction of aliphatic disulphide depends on

the pH of the medium as proposed by Manousek and Zuman⁵. It could be represented as follows.

In pH range < 5 :

In pH range 5–8 :

In pH range 8–10 :

where the product of reduction is stabilised by the presence of thiolate ion in alkaline medium.

(b) Reduction of aromatic disulphides is similar to that of aliphatic disulphides except that the reduction process stops at the production of thiol group at all the pHs examined where the Ar-S bond is stabilised by resonance. Thus, the reduction mechanism of *p*-tolyl disulphide could be represented as

Experimental

Benzyl disulphide and *p*-tolyl disulphide of pure grade (Eastman Organic Chemicals, U.S.A.) were used as such. Other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Polarograms were obtained using Metrohm E506 polarecord with a polarographic stand E505 DC. The pH values were measured both before and after recording the polarograms. The capillary characteristics were $m = 1.77 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t = 3.4 \text{ s}$ per drop. All polarograms were recorded using saturated Ag/AgCl electrode as reference with platinum electrode as auxiliary electrode at $25 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

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